

GEOPOLITICISING NORMATIVE POWER: POLITICAL ADAPTATION AND STRATEGIC TRANSFORMATION IN EU FOREIGN POLICY

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This article analyses the discourse on a 'geopolitical Europe' and examines whether it represents a transformation of European Union foreign policy or a strategic adaptation of its normative project to conditions of great-power rivalry. Integrating theories of normative power, realist critique, and European integration, the study addresses a gap in the literature by focusing on long-term political and institutional dynamics rather than isolated crises. Based on qualitative analysis of EU strategic documents and scholarly sources, the article identifies three phases: the development of strategic capacity, the pragmatic turn after 2016, and the acceleration of geopolitical discourse following the war in Ukraine. It argues that the EU's geopoliticisation reflects incremental political adaptation rather than a paradigmatic shift. The Union is thus emerging as a hybrid actor combining normative ambitions with strategic instruments of power, while the limits of this transformation remain rooted in its intergovernmental decision-making structure.

Key words: European Union; foreign policy; normative power; hybrid actorness; strategic adaptation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The shifting international environment of the first decades of the 21st century has fundamentally altered the character of the European Union's foreign and security policy. While the post-Cold War era saw the Union frequently interpreted as a normative or civilian actor—whose influence derived primarily from economic regulation, multilateral diplomacy, and the promotion of liberal values—contemporary scholarly discourse increasingly points towards its 'geopolitical awakening' (Manners 2002; Smith 2008; Hyde-Price 2006). This shift reflects not only a change in the discourse of European leaders but also broader structural

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transformations of the global system, characterised by the return of power rivalry, regional fragmentation, and intensifying strategic competition (Biscop 2016; Riddervold and Rieker 2024). From an analytical perspective, however, this is not merely a reaction to external threats; it is also a consequence of the gradual politicisation of European integration, in which questions of identity, sovereignty, and strategic autonomy have become subjects of domestic political contestation and the redefinition of collective European actorness.

The debate over the EU's geopolitical transformation further reflects broader theoretical tensions between different interpretations of European integration and its international agency. Within the literature on European studies, two dominant analytical frameworks can be identified. The first, represented by the concept of Normative Power Europe, emphasises the Union's capacity to shape the international environment through norms, rules, and economic integration, where the legitimisation of European actorness is closely intertwined with a value-based discourse (Manners 2002; Sjursen 2006). The second approach, which has gained prominence in recent years, interprets the EU's development through a more realist geopolitical framework, highlighting power competition, security threats, and strategic autonomy (Kagan 2007; Hyde-Price 2013; Biscop 2016; Keukeleire and Delreux 2022; Šrobárova and Belan 2026). The rising popularity of this perspective is linked to shifts in the global distribution of power and the increasing pressure on the EU to respond to a conflictual environment without relying exclusively on multilateral mechanisms.

Despite the growing body of literature, the question remains whether the discourse on a 'geopolitical Europe' represents a genuine transformation of the Union's foreign and security policy or rather an adaptation of the existing normative project to the new conditions of the international system. Significantly, a substantial portion of research focuses on individual strategic documents or specific crises, while paying less attention to the long-term political processes unfolding within European institutions and among Member States (Hooghe and Marks 2019; Schimmelfennig 2024). Consequently, the broader context of the transformation of European actorness is often lost—a context that includes internal conflicts over the direction of integration, diverging strategic cultures, and the shifting political priorities of national governments. It is precisely this domestic political dimension that is crucial for understanding both the limits and possibilities of the EU's geopolitical turn.

Existing research largely concentrates on individual crises or specific policies, often failing to reflect the cumulative impact of systemic factors—multipolar competition, regional instability, and internal political divergences between Member States—on the long-term transformation of the Union's foreign policy identity. The synthesis of these dimensions represents the analytical gap that this article seeks to fill. The objective is to examine the extent to which current developments can be understood as a shift from a normative model towards a hybrid form of geopolitical actorness, in which elements of value-oriented policy and realist strategic rationality converge (Biscop 2016; Tocci 2017). Thus, this analytical framework links the discussion on geopolitics with questions of power, legitimacy, and collective decision-making within integration projects.

Considering the above, the primary research question of this article is: To what extent does the geopolitical awakening of the European Union represent a structural transformation of its foreign and security policy, and to what extent is it a discursive adaptation of its normative identity to a changing global environment? The article argues that the geopolitical turn should not be understood as a radical rupture, but rather as a process of incremental strategic

adaptation, in which normative elements are combined with pragmatic and power-oriented instruments (Blockmans and Koutrakos 2018; Voskopoulos 2020). Such an argument allows for the analysis of European policy development not only as a response to external threats but also as the result of domestic political negotiations, discursive shifts, and institutional evolution.

Methodologically, this study employs a qualitative analysis based on the content-related and comparative interpretation of primary EU strategic documents and relevant scholarly literature. The analytical framework bridges theories of normative power, realist approaches to geopolitics, and perspectives on European integration, enabling an examination of not only discursive changes but also their translation into specific policy and institutional measures (Manners 2002; Hyde-Price 2013; Moravcsik 1998). The emphasis on interpreting decision-making processes reflects the multi-level nature of European governance, where national interests, supranational institutions, and broader geopolitical pressures intersect.

The research framework designed in this manner allows for the identification of long-term trends in the transformation of EU foreign and security policy, while simultaneously assessing the limits of its geopolitical ambition. From a political science perspective, the contribution of this article lies in connecting the geopolitical debate with the analysis of European integration and in the argument that the geopolitical awakening cannot be understood in isolation from the Union's internal political dynamics. Thus, the article contributes to the broader academic discourse on the nature of European actorness and the adaptation of regional integration projects to a changing global order (Westlake 2020; van Middelaar 2021).

The article is structured as follows. The first section develops the theoretical framework and analyses the transition from the concept of normative power to a geopolitical interpretation of European actorness. The second section examines the institutional and strategic development of EU foreign and security policy. The third section explores pragmatic adaptation following the adoption of the EU Global Strategy and the strengthening of the concepts of resilience and the integrated approach. The fourth section analyses the acceleration of geopolitical transformation in the context of contemporary global crises and military conflicts. Finally, the conclusion synthesises the main findings and discusses the implications for the future trajectory of the EU as a political actor.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: FROM NORMATIVE POWER TO THE GEOPOLITICAL ACTORNESS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

The question of the European Union's nature as an international actor represents one of the most widely debated topics within the literature of European studies and international relations theory. Since the inception of the integration project, debates on European actorness have fluctuated between interpreting the Union as a unique normative project and a more realist understanding of its behaviour as a response to the structural pressures of the international system. Following the end of the Cold War, the EU was frequently interpreted through the concepts of civilian and normative power, which emphasised its capacity to shape the international environment through rules, norms, and economic integration rather than the traditional instruments of military force (Smith 2008; Sjørusen 2006).

The most significant contribution to this debate is the concept of 'Normative Power Europe', formulated by Ian Manners, which highlights the Union's ability to promote its values through the diffusion of norms and the social transformation of the international environment (Manners 2002; Manners 2006). From a political science perspective, the EU appeared as an actor whose identity was closely intertwined with the project of post-sovereign integration and the notion that the legitimacy of international action could derive from rules and values rather than material power.

This normative interpretation of European actorness assumed that the integration project represented an alternative to traditional power politics founded on rivalry and security dilemmas. Scholars such as Karen E. Smith and Nathalie Tocci have pointed out that EU foreign policy is inextricably linked to multilateralism, the promotion of democracy, and the rule of law, with its legitimacy stemming from a combination of economic influence and regulatory capacity (Smith 2008; Tocci 2017). In this view, the Union was understood as an actor whose power originated from institutionalised cooperation and normative attractiveness rather than military dominance. This created an image of the EU as a 'post-Westphalian' actor that challenged classical realist understandings of international politics (Manners 2002). This approach dominated particularly during periods of relative stability in the global order, when liberal multilateralism appeared to provide a sufficient framework for European foreign policy, allowing European actorness to be interpreted as a model of normatively oriented integration.

However, with the gradual return of geopolitical rivalry, a systematic critique of the normative approach began to emerge. Adrian Hyde-Price and other realist-oriented authors cautioned that interpreting the EU as a normative actor underestimates the significance of power, security, and strategic interests (Hyde-Price 2006; Hyde-Price 2013). According to this perspective, while the Union is a unique political entity, it remains part of an anarchic international system that compels it to respond to power challenges in a manner like traditional states. Significantly, realist critique does not dispute the existence of normative elements in European policy; rather, it highlights their limited effectiveness in an environment of escalating strategic competition. The growing rivalry between great powers, the destabilisation of neighbouring regions, and the weakening of multilateral institutions have gradually created conditions in which a purely normative model has proven analytically insufficient to explain the EU's behaviour. This has opened the way for a reinterpretation of European actorness in geopolitical categories (Kagan 2007; Riddervold and Rieker 2024).

Authors examining the Union's strategic culture and political identity have also responded to this shift. Sven Biscop and Steven Blockmans emphasise that European foreign policy is progressively moving towards a more realist understanding of security, while simultaneously retaining its normative elements (Biscop 2016; Blockmans and Koutrakos 2018). Similarly, Koops and Pacheco Pardo point to the growing geopolitisation of European policy, manifested not only in the discourse on strategic autonomy but also in the nexus of economic, technological, and security instruments (Peráček 2021; Koops and Pacheco Pardo 2023; Šrobárova and Belan 2026). These analyses suggest that the EU is increasingly oscillating between two analytical poles—normative identity and geopolitical rationality—where the resulting form of its actorness emerges through political compromises between Member States and institutional processes typical of multi-level governance.

From a theoretical perspective, the current transformation can thus be

interpreted as a tension between constructivist and realist approaches. The constructivist perspective highlights the role of identity, values, and social norms in shaping EU external policy, whereas the realist tradition underscores the structural limits of the normative project in an environment of strategic competition. Several scholars, including Tocci and others, therefore propose understanding the EU's development not as a transition from one paradigm to another, but as the gradual formation of a hybrid model of actorness, in which normative and geopolitical elements complement each other (Tocci 2017). This is a process of redefining the Union's identity resulting from the interaction between internal institutional dynamics and external geopolitical pressures, further suggesting a need to transcend traditional dichotomies between idealism and realism in the analysis of European integration.

The concept of a geopolitical turn, therefore, does not signify a total abandonment of normative power, but rather its reinterpretation within the context of power politics. The discourse on strategic autonomy, resilience, and the 'language of power' promoted by EU officials indicates a shift towards a more pragmatic approach, where normative goals are intertwined with geopolitical interests. As Biscop notes, European strategy is increasingly oriented towards protecting its own interests and stabilising the neighbourhood, reflecting a more realist understanding of the international environment (Biscop 2016). Analytically significant is the fact that this shift is occurring within existing EU institutional structures, which continue to emphasise consensual decision-making and a multilateral approach, thereby creating tension between geopolitical ambition and normative identity.

Furthermore, it must be emphasised that the EU's hybrid nature as both a supranational and intergovernmental actor creates specific limits to its geopolitical agency. Unlike traditional states, the Union does not derive its actions from a singular strategic culture, but from pluralistic national perspectives that shape its foreign policy (Hooghe and Marks 2019; Brhlíková and Kočnerová 2020). It is precisely this institutional context that explains why the EU's geopolitical ambitions often coexist with a continued emphasis on norms and multilateral rules. Consequently, any analysis must account not only for theoretical debates on power and identity but also for the internal dynamics of European integration, which determine the possibilities for collective action and limit the pace of strategic adaptation.

Based on these theoretical discussions, this article operates on the assumption that the EU's geopolitical awakening represents a process of the gradual geopolitisation of a normative project, rather than its replacement by a realist logic. The analytical framework thus combines the concept of normative power (Manners), realist critique (Hyde-Price), and the perspective of strategic adaptation (Tocci, Biscop), enabling the examination of the transformation of European foreign policy as a hybrid process unfolding between values and power (Manners 2002; Hyde-Price 2013; Biscop 2016; Tocci 2017). This theoretical framework also provides an analytical bridge to the subsequent chapter, which demonstrates how these theoretical tensions have translated into the specific institutional and strategic development of the European Union's foreign and security policy.

3 INSTITUTIONAL AND STRATEGIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE EUROPEAN UNION'S FOREIGN AND SECURITY POLICY

The institutional development of the European Union's foreign and security policy represents a key prerequisite for its gradual transformation from a normatively oriented actor into an entity with growing geopolitical ambitions. Since the early 1990s, Member States have sought to create a framework that would allow the Union to act in a more coordinated manner within the international environment while simultaneously maintaining the intergovernmental nature of decision-making. This duality—between the logic of integration and the sovereignty of Member States—has fundamentally shaped the pace and direction of the strategic evolution of European foreign policy (Moravcsik 1998; Blockmans and Koutrakos 2018; Westlake 2020). It constitutes a classic example of multi-level governance, where supranational ambitions intersect with national preferences and domestic political constraints (Hooghe and Marks 2019). The tension between these two logics explains why EU institutional innovations often manifest as incremental adjustments to existing mechanisms rather than radical reforms aimed at centralising foreign policy. This evolutionary character of integration further suggests that the Union's geopolitical transformation is inextricably linked to the political dynamics of its Member States and their willingness to delegate competences to the European level.

The establishment of the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) following the adoption of the Maastricht Treaty represented the first systematic attempt at the political coordination of the Union's external action (Smith 2008; Hill and Smith 2017). Despite ambitious rhetoric, however, practical implementation revealed significant limits to collective action, arising from the diverging strategic cultures and security priorities of individual states. The experience of the Balkan conflicts in the 1990s underscored a lack of both operational capacity and political cohesion, thereby stimulating debate on the need to develop common defence instruments and to institutionally strengthen the foreign policy dimension of integration (Howorth 2014; Biscop 2016). These events also demonstrated that the normative discourse on European actorness must be complemented by a political capacity to act in crisis situations, which gradually led to a redefinition of expectations regarding the Union as a political actor. Analytically, this moment can be understood as the first significant shift from symbolic diplomacy towards the strategic operationalisation of shared goals (Hyde-Price 2013).

The subsequent period was characterised by the gradual construction of an institutional architecture designed to enhance the coherence of European actorness. The creation of the position of High Representative, the establishment of the European External Action Service (EEAS), and the development of the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) represented an attempt to overcome the fragmentation between diplomatic, security, and developmental instruments (Blockmans and Koutrakos 2018; Duke 2019). Crucially, these reforms signalled an effort to move from purely interstate coordination towards a hybrid model of governance, in which European institutions gain a greater role in formulating strategic priorities, while Member States retain the final word. This hybrid model also reflects the broader evolution of European integration, where the legitimisation of common policies relies on a combination of supranational expertise and national political control (Hooghe and Marks 2019). In a broader context, this involves the gradual formation of an institutional

infrastructure that, while not moving the Union towards a federal model of foreign policy, nevertheless increases its capacity for strategic coordination.

From a theoretical perspective, this development can be interpreted as a gradual shift from a purely normative model towards strategic adaptation. As Biscop points out, European strategic documents as early as the first decade of the 21st century indicated a more realist perception of the security environment, even though the language of multilateral cooperation remained dominant (Biscop 2016). The development of civilian and military missions, as well as the creation of EU Battlegroups, signalled an ambition to expand the spectrum of foreign policy instruments beyond economic and regulatory power (Koops and Pacheco Pardo 2023). These steps can be interpreted as a process of the gradual socialisation of Member States into a common strategic mindset, which, however, unfolded within existing institutional limits and never fully replaced national security paradigms. This process also demonstrates that the EU's strategic culture does not emerge through one-off decisions but rather as the result of long-term political interactions between Member States and European institutions.

The Lisbon Treaty represented another significant milestone, as it strengthened institutional cohesion and created new mechanisms for coordination between Member States and European institutions. The unification of the roles of High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy and Vice-President of the European Commission was intended to enhance strategic coherence and link various dimensions of external policy. The Lisbon reform can thus be understood as an attempt to bridge the tension between supranational and intergovernmental models of integration; the result was a compromise institutional design that bolstered coordination without fundamentally undermining national sovereignty (Blockmans and Koutrakos 2018; Westlake 2020). Despite these reforms, however, foreign and security policy remained an area heavily dependent on the political will of Member States, which continued to limit the EU's ability to act swiftly and decisively in situations requiring strategic decisions (Hyde-Price 2013). This paradox—growing institutional capacity coupled with persistent political fragmentation—represents one of the defining characteristics of European geopolitical actorness.

An important element of institutional development was also the gradual formation of a strategic culture. The 2003 European Security Strategy represented an attempt to define a shared perception of threats and the EU's role in the international environment. The document reflected the post-Cold War optimism and emphasised the Union's role as a promoter of stability and a multilateral order (Council of the European Union 2003; Biscop 2016). Subsequent strategic initiatives, however, progressively shifted the focus towards the protection of European interests and the strengthening of defence capabilities, thereby paving the way for the pragmatic turn that fully manifested after 2016 (Tocci 2017). This evolution suggests that the EU's geopolitical awakening was not a sudden rupture but the result of a long-term process of political adaptation, involving changes not only in rhetoric but also in institutional expectations regarding the Union as an actor capable of responding to an unstable international environment.

Institutional development thus laid the foundation for geopolitical transformation yet simultaneously revealed its structural limits. The intergovernmental nature of decision-making, multi-level governance, differing strategic priorities, and the asymmetry of military capabilities among Member States mean that the EU remains a hybrid actor whose geopolitical ambitions are

always contingent upon internal consensus (Brhlíková and Kočnerová 2020; Riddervold and Rieker 2024). This state can be interpreted because of the specific nature of European integration, which combines elements of federal and interstate models, creating a dynamic of constant negotiation between effectiveness and legitimacy (Hooghe and Marks 2019). It is this combination of increasing strategic capacity and persistent institutional constraints that explains why the Union's geopolitical awakening manifests as incremental adaptations rather than radical transformation, and why its foreign policy remains firmly anchored in the political dynamics of the Member States. This institutional context also provides an analytical bridge to the following chapter, which demonstrates how these long-term structural changes translated into the pragmatic adaptation of European foreign policy after 2016.

4 PRAGMATIC ADAPTATION OF EU FOREIGN POLICY: FROM MULTILATERALISM TO STRATEGIC RESILIENCE

While the previous chapter analysed the institutional and strategic prerequisites for the gradual geopolitisation of European actorness, the following section focuses on the moment when this process began to manifest in concrete strategic practice and the discursive adaptation of EU foreign policy. The period following the mid-2010s represents a significant juncture in the evolution of the European Union's foreign and security policy, as normative discourse began to be progressively complemented by a more pragmatic understanding of strategic interests (Biscop 2016; Tocci 2017). This development cannot be explained solely by changes in the international environment; it is also a product of the Union's internal political dynamics, which responded to a cumulative series of economic, migration, and security crises.

Analytically, it is significant that this involves not only a change in instruments but a transformation in how the EU defines its role within the international system and how Member States interpret shared strategic priorities. The pragmatic turn can thus be understood as the result of an interaction between external geopolitical pressures and internal processes of political coordination, which are gradually shifting the balance between normative identity and strategic realism (Ilik and Adamczyk 2025; Costa and Barbé 2025). Furthermore, this process highlights the overall developmental dynamics of the EU, in which the integration project adapts to the changing expectations of domestic political actors, party systems, and voter preferences within Member States, thereby influencing the redefinition of foreign policy priorities at the European level (Riddervold and Rieker 2024).

The adoption of the EU Global Strategy (EUGS) in 2016 can be interpreted as an attempt to redefine European actorness under conditions of increasing geopolitical uncertainty. The document explicitly characterised the international environment as more complex and conflict-prone, signalling a departure from the optimistic vision of a multilateral order characteristic of the preceding period (European External Action Service 2016). Importantly, the strategy did not abandon the normative foundations of European policy but reinterpreted them through the concept of pragmatism. As Tocci points out, the pragmatic turn represented an effort to combine value-based ambitions with a realistic assessment of the strategic environment (Tocci 2017).

This shift can also be understood as an attempt to bridge the diverging strategic preferences of Member States, which, following a series of crises, increasingly

sought a more flexible framework for collective action. At the same time, it serves as an example of discursive adaptation, where new concepts and strategic frameworks facilitate the legitimisation of an incremental shift in political priorities without an explicit rejection of prior normative principles (Costa and Barbé 2025). In this sense, the Global Strategy did not represent a radical rupture but rather a redefinition of the existing political consensus through a new analytical language.

Resilience emerged as the pivotal analytical concept of this period, gradually superseding the more ambitious discourse of transforming neighbouring regions (Juncos 2017). Resilience was defined as the capacity of states and societies to manage crises and adapt to an unstable environment (Juncos 2017; Rehak et al. 2024), thereby shifting EU foreign policy from the normative export of models towards the promotion of stability. This shift can be interpreted as a reaction to the limits of European transformative power and, simultaneously, as an adaptation to a pluralistic international system in which the EU lacks the capacity for the unilateral shaping of the external environment (Hyde-Price 2013). Furthermore, the concept of resilience reflects a broader trend in European policy, where emphasis is moving away from the ambition to change the external environment towards an effort to manage uncertainty and reduce political and economic vulnerabilities. From a theoretical perspective, this shift can also be interpreted as a transition from a transformative logic to a logic of risk management, which is characteristic of contemporary forms of global governance and alters expectations of the Union as an external actor (Koops and Pacheco Pardo 2023).

Concurrently, the nature of the Union's multilateral orientation underwent a gradual transformation. In place of the universalist promotion of global rules, a 'selective multilateralism' based on strategic partnerships and regional stabilisation increasingly took hold (Biscop 2018). This trend reflects the growing geopolitisation of European policy, as decision-making began to account more heavily for issues of security, energy dependence, and technological competition. However, the pragmatic turn did not signify an abandonment of multilateralism; rather, it represented its reformulation within an environment of power rivalry. This evolution suggests a shift from normative universalism towards a more contextual form of cooperation, in which strategic interests and value-based principles are mutually contingent, creating a hybrid model of foreign policy behaviour. This hybrid approach enables Member States to maintain a degree of strategic flexibility without the need for total institutional centralisation (Riddervold and Rieker 2024).

From the perspective of EU institutional politics, the pragmatic shift also represented an effort to achieve better coordination among various foreign policy instruments. The 'integrated approach' to conflict and crisis resolution emphasised the nexus between diplomacy, development cooperation, security measures, and economic policy (European External Action Service 2016). Crucially, this process also revealed the persistent limits of the decision-making system, as Member States frequently interpreted strategic priorities differently and preferred varying forms of engagement in neighbouring regions. Pragmatic adaptation, therefore, did not lead to the full centralisation of foreign policy but rather to a more flexible model of coordination that allows for the combination of supranational initiatives with national strategies, reflecting the pluralistic nature of the European political space (Hooghe and Marks 2019). This model further indicates that the EU's geopolitical transformation is closely intertwined with political compromises between Member States, which remain the primary bearers of strategic legitimacy and decision-making authority.

The transformation of discourse after 2016 thus suggests the emergence of a hybrid model of European actorness that fuses normative values with a more realist understanding of geopolitics (Manners 2002; Tocci 2017). The concepts of resilience and selective multilateralism can be seen as indicators of this transformation, demonstrating how the EU seeks to adapt to a world characterised by strategic competition without entirely abandoning its identity as a normative actor (Biscop 2018; Costa and Barbé 2025). This development also paved the way for more pronounced geopolitical rhetoric and concrete policy measures that fully manifested in response to the global crises of the early 2020s. Within the analytical logic of this article, pragmatic adaptation represents a transitional phase between long-term institutional development and the accelerated geopolitical transformation that will be the subject of the following chapter.

5 THE GEOPOLITICAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE EUROPEAN UNION IN THE CONTEXT OF WAR AND SYSTEMIC RIVALRY

While the third chapter demonstrated how pragmatic adaptation and the concept of resilience became established within the Union's strategic discourse, the following section analyses the moment when external systemic shocks accelerated the geopolitisation of European policy, shifting it from strategic reflection to concrete political action. The beginning of the third decade of the 21st century represents a turning point in the debate over the nature of the European Union's foreign and security policy. A combination of the COVID-19 pandemic, deepening technological and economic rivalry between great powers, and, most significantly, Russia's full-scale military aggression against Ukraine has fundamentally altered the strategic environment in which the EU operates (Schimmelfennig 2024; Riddervold and Rieker 2024; Kirkegaard 2025).

Significantly, it is not merely the events themselves that matter, but the way these crises have redefined the understanding of European actorness and legitimised the discourse on a 'geopolitical Europe'. This involves a process in which geopolitical language is progressively becoming part of the Union's political identity and, simultaneously, a tool for mobilising political support among Member States (Hoeffler, Hofmann and Mérand 2024; Håkansson 2024). This discursive shift also reflects a broader trend of the politicisation of EU foreign policy, as issues of security, energy sovereignty, and strategic autonomy move to the centre of domestic political debates and influence the dynamics of European integration.

From a theoretical perspective, the war in Ukraine can be interpreted as an external shock that accelerated the process of the geopolitisation of European policy (Riddervold and Rieker 2024; Schimmelfennig 2024; Hoeffler, Hofmann and Mérand 2024). According to realist approaches, such systemic events represent moments when international actors re-evaluate their strategies and identities in response to shifts in the balance of power. In the case of the EU, this process has manifested not only in political decisions but also in a change in the discursive framework, as Union officials began to openly speak about the need to 'learn the language of power' (Borrell 2020a; Borrell 2020b). This shift suggests that geopolitical rationality is increasingly becoming a legitimate component of European foreign policy, with the discourse of geopolitics serving to overcome long-standing political divisions between Member States and to forge a minimum consensus on strategic priorities. This process should be understood as a form of

discursive institutionalisation, in which the language of geopolitics legitimises new political expectations without the need for fundamental institutional reform.

One of the most visible manifestations of this transformation has been the reinterpretation of economic and energy interdependence (Sapir, Kirkegaard and Zettelmeyer 2025). While in previous decades, interdependence was perceived primarily as a tool for stability and peace, contemporary debate increasingly views it as a potential source of vulnerability. This represents a significant shift from the liberal logic of economic cooperation towards a more realist perception of international political economy, in which trade, investment, and technological supply chains acquire a security dimension. This process of the geopolitisation of economic policy further suggests an expansion of the spectrum of instruments through which the EU promotes its strategic interests, as the boundary between economic regulation and security policy progressively blurs. This development can also be understood as a manifestation of the securitisation of economic policies, which alters the way decisions are legitimised at the European level and strengthens the role of executive institutions in defining strategic priorities.

The war in Ukraine has also bolstered the discourse on strategic autonomy, which is gradually moving from academic debate into practical policy. The acceleration of this geopolitical turn, however, remains unevenly distributed across the Union, reflecting divergent strategic priorities and historical experiences of Member States. While the frontline states in Central and Eastern Europe—driven by an existential perception of the Russian threat—advocate for a rapid expansion of hard power instruments and a robust enlargement policy, traditional neutral states or those in the Southern neighbourhood often prioritize a more cautious approach, emphasizing the preservation of economic stability and non-military crisis management. These internal cleavages create a 'variable geometry' of geopoliticisation, where the pace of collective action is frequently dictated by the need to find a minimum common denominator between those pushing for a 'geopolitical awakening' and those wary of undermining long-standing strategic cultures.

Beyond traditional security concerns, the EU's ability to act as a cohesive geopolitical actor is further strained by the proliferation of disinformation and conspiracy theories that undermine the democratic foundations of Member States (Kukovič et al. 2024; Ivančík and Andrassy 2024), disrupt the functioning of democratic institutions, increase polarization in society, and at the same time arouse distrust in governments and public authorities in their ability to address emerging problems (Haček 2024; Ivančík and Andrassy 2025). These narratives often exploit societal divisions, fostering scepticism towards European institutions and complicating the formation of a unified strategic response to external threats (Beňuška and Nečas 2021; Csanyi and Kucharčík 2023). As research suggests, the demographic susceptibility to such conspiratorial beliefs varies significantly across the Union, creating additional internal friction points that hinder the implementation of a robust and coherent foreign policy). Consequently, the geopolitisation of the Union is not merely an external challenge but is deeply intertwined with the task of safeguarding domestic political stability against manipulative information environments.

The adoption of the Strategic Compass and the increased emphasis on defence investments can be interpreted as an effort by the EU to respond to a changing security environment without entirely abandoning the transatlantic framework of cooperation (European Union 2022; Koops and Pacheco Pardo 2023). In this context, it is significant that strategic autonomy does not manifest as a quest for

total independence, but rather as a process of redefining relations between Member States and external partners under conditions of geopolitical rivalry (Ilik and Adamczyk 2025). This discourse simultaneously creates a new space for domestic political negotiation regarding the level of integration in the fields of defence and security, highlighting the enduring significance of national political preferences, coalition compromises, and domestic political calculations in shaping common policy.

Furthermore, the character of enlargement and neighbourhood policy is also changing, as these are increasingly interpreted as instruments of geopolitical leverage. Granting candidate status to Ukraine and Moldova can be understood not only as a normative gesture of solidarity but also as a strategic step aimed at stabilising the Eastern Neighbourhood and strengthening the EU's political presence in the region (Anghel 2025). This development confirms the argument that the EU's geopolitical turn does not consist in replacing normative identity with a realist logic, but in their gradual synthesis. Enlargement is thus once again becoming a political tool that links the integration project with geopolitical considerations of stability and security, while simultaneously strengthening the internal legitimacy of European integration by redefining its strategic borders.

Despite these shifts, however, the Union's geopolitical transformation remains limited by its institutional nature. Decision-making in the field of foreign and security policy is still largely dependent on the consensus of Member States, creating tension between the ambition to act as a geopolitical actor and the reality of pluralistic national interests (Bickerton, Hodson and Puetter 2015; Keukeleire and Delreux 2022). The hybrid nature of the EU is thus also evident in its response to the war: on the one hand, there is unprecedented coordination of sanctions and security support; on the other, differences in strategic priorities and threat perceptions persist (Riddervold and Rieker 2024; Håkansson 2024). This illustrates that geopolitical transformation unfolds within existing institutional constraints and is the result of incremental political compromises that define the pace and scope of integration.

The EU's geopolitical awakening can thus be interpreted as a process of the gradual institutionalisation of realist elements within the normative project of European integration. The war in Ukraine does not represent the start of this transformation, but rather a moment that accelerated it and simultaneously revealed its limits. The EU is thus increasingly positioning itself as a hybrid actor moving between normative identity and geopolitical rationality, while the resulting form of its foreign policy remains a subject of ongoing political and academic debate. This development also creates an analytical bridge to the article's final synthesis, which evaluates the Union's geopolitical awakening as a political process occurring at the intersection of integration, identity, and strategic adaptation.

6 CONCLUSION

The synthesis of the theoretical, institutional, and empirical analysis presented in the preceding chapters demonstrates that the geopolitical awakening of the European Union should not be understood as a radical departure from its normative identity, but rather as a gradual process shaped by the interaction of identity, power, and institutional adaptation to a changing international environment. At the core of this transformation lies the tension between the normative tradition of European integration and the increasing necessity to

respond to geopolitical rivalry, regional instability, and the internal political divergences of Member States. The developments of recent years confirm that the EU is not shifting from one paradigm to another but is progressively forming a hybrid model of actorhood that combines value-based ambitions with pragmatic instruments of power. This hybrid character can be understood as a specific response to the dilemma between integration and sovereignty—a tension that has long been constitutive of the European project and which simultaneously defines both the limits and the possibilities of the Union's geopolitical transformation. From this perspective, geopoliticisation does not represent the negation of the integration project, but rather its evolutionary adaptation to the conditions of a shifting global order.

In this context, it is crucial to recognise that the Union's geopolitical transformation is not the result of a single strategic decision, but the consequence of the cumulative impact of external shocks and internal institutional changes. Institutional development—from the Maastricht Treaty through the Lisbon reforms to current strategic initiatives—has created a framework that allows the EU to respond more flexibly to crisis situations while preserving its intergovernmental character. This duality explains why the Union's geopolitical ambitions often coexist with persistent limits on collective decision-making, and why geopolitical rationality asserts itself through gradual discursive and institutional shifts rather than fundamental ruptures. The geopoliticisation of European policy, therefore, does not signify a weakening of the integration project, but its adaptation to the conditions of a pluralistic and conflict-prone international environment, where political legitimacy derives from the capacity to respond to uncertainty.

The pragmatic turn following the adoption of the EU Global Strategy and the subsequent geopoliticisation of economic, energy, and security policy indicates a shift towards a more realist perception of the international environment. The concepts of resilience and selective multilateralism further suggest that the EU is attempting to adapt without entirely abandoning its normative foundations. The war in Ukraine has accelerated this process by legitimising the discourse of strategic autonomy and strengthening the perception of the Union as a political actor capable of coordinated action. Nevertheless, the response of Member States has shown that the geopolitical awakening remains contingent upon an internal plurality of strategic preferences, which is an inherent part of the European political system and will continue to shape the pace of further integration in foreign policy.

The acceleration of this geopolitical turn, however, remains unevenly distributed across the Union, reflecting divergent strategic priorities and historical experiences of Member States. While the frontline states in Central and Eastern Europe—driven by an existential perception of the Russian threat—advocate for a rapid expansion of hard power instruments, traditional neutral states or those in the Southern neighbourhood often prioritise a more cautious approach. These internal cleavages are further complicated by domestic political dynamics, where institutional (dis)trust and the rise of alternative political narratives can influence national positions on collective European security measures. This creates a 'variable geometry' of geopoliticisation, where the pace of strategic adaptation is frequently dictated by the need to find a minimum common denominator between those pushing for a 'geopolitical awakening' and those wary of undermining long-standing strategic cultures. This evolution reveals that the EU's geopolitical transformation is primarily a political process of negotiation and compromise, rather than a linear transition to a realist paradigm.

The contribution of this article lies in its interpretation of the EU's geopolitical transformation not as a transition from normative power to realist actorness, but as a process of the geopoliticisation of the normative project itself. Such an analytical framework allows for the transcendence of the dichotomy between idealistic and realistic interpretations of European foreign policy, while highlighting the political nature of the decision-making processes that shape the resulting form of European actorness. In the broader context of European studies, this approach underscores the importance of internal political dynamics, discursive shifts, and institutional compromises, which often remain in the shadow of discussions focused exclusively on geopolitical factors. The article thus contributes to the ongoing discourse on how regional integration projects respond to the changing distribution of power in the international system and how their identity is transformed under conditions of systemic rivalry.

The findings of this article suggest that the future development of EU foreign and security policy will depend primarily on the ability of Member States to forge a political consensus on strategic priorities, rather than merely on the adoption of new strategic documents. At the same time, the analysis indicates that it remains an open question whether the emerging hybrid model of actorness represents a stable long-term configuration or rather a transitional phase shaped by current systemic pressures and crises. For future research, this implies a need for greater attention to the nexus between domestic political processes within Member States and the formation of common foreign policy, as well as an exploration of the conditions under which this hybrid model can be sustained over time. The European Union thus remains a unique political project, whose geopolitical transformation is an open-ended process rather than a closed phase of integration, offering a vital empirical case for broader academic discussions on the adaptation of regional organisations to a changing world order.

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GEOPOLITIZACIJA NORMATIVNE MOČI: POLITIČNA ADAPTACIJA IN STRATEŠKA TRANSFORMACIJA V ZUNANJI POLITIKI EU

Članek analizira naraščajoči diskurz o »geopolitični Evropi« in preučuje, ali to predstavlja temeljno preobrazbo zunanje politike Evropske unije ali strateško prilagoditev njenega normativnega projekta razmeram zaostrenega rivalstva med velesilami in večpolarne konkurence. S povezovanjem teorij normativne moči, realističnih kritik in pristopov k evropskemu povezovanju prispevek naslavlja raziskovalno vrzel v obstoječi literaturi in dokazuje, da je geopolitizacija Unije rezultat postopne politične adaptacije in ne paradigmskega premika. Na podlagi kvalitativne analize relevantne znanstvene literature, strateških dokumentov in institucionalnih razvojov članek identificira tri ključne faze: izgradnjo strateške zmogljivosti, pragmatični obrat po letu 2016 in pospešitev geopolitičnega diskurza v kontekstu vojne v Ukrajini. Avtor trdi, da se EU razvija v hibridnega akterja, ki združuje normativne ambicije z instrumenti strateške moči, čeprav meje tega premika izvirajo iz medvladne narave odločanja. Posledično prispevek ponuja posodobljeno interpretacijo geopolitizacije evropske akterstva z vidika politologije.

Ključne besede: Evropska unija, zunanja politika, normativna moč, geopolitizacija, hibridno akterstvo, strateška adaptacija.